

INVESTIGATIONS OF INTERFACIAL ADHESION BETWEEN PZT FIBERS AND EPOXY MATRICES

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1 Introduction

Lead zirconate titanate (PZT) is a ceramic material with pronounced piezoelectric properties and therefore used in actuation and sensing applications [1]. PZT fibers are applied in electromechanical transducers such as Active Fiber Composites (AFC) and serve as the piezoelectrically active component. AFCs usually consist of a monolayer of piezoelectric fibers arranged in parallel in a polymeric matrix (typically epoxy resins). Surface electrodes on both sides allow for the application or detection of electric fields [2].

Sensors and actuators made of PZT fibers have distinct advantages compared to monolithic piezoelectric devices. Due to the brittleness of PZT, fibers are easier to handle without damage than bulk material. Also, a composite of PZT fibers and a polymeric matrix is more flexible and robust in contrast to monolithic piezoelectric devices. Therefore, AFCs are more suitable for applications in curved structures. Furthermore, using PZT fibers instead of wafers allows for weight savings and a stronger longitudinal effect [2, 3].

Piezoelectric devices are capable of transforming electrical energy into mechanical energy (actuation) and vice versa (sensing). Hence, AFCs can be used for vibration suppression, noise control, contour control and structural health monitoring [1, 4]. Among other parameters, the performance of AFCs significantly depends on the interfacial adhesion between the PZT fibers and the polymeric matrix. For example, the transformation of an electric signal into an ultrasonic sound is considerably influenced by the level of bonding between fibers and matrix.

Hence, this work is concerned with the determination and improvement of the interfacial adhesion between one type of PZT fibers of 290 μm in diameter and a selection of epoxy resin matrices.

For this, the single-fiber fragmentation test (SFFT) [5] has been chosen to experimentally determine the interfacial adhesion (see Fig. 1). Apart from measuring the differences in adhesion between the PZT fibers and several epoxy resin matrices, the application of customized surface modifications to the fiber surfaces is envisaged to investigate their influence on interfacial adhesion. Surface modifications of polyurethane- or epoxy-based compatible coatings with silane coupling agents will be reported.

2 Experimental

Several micromechanical methods exist for the determination of interfacial adhesion such as the single-fiber pull-out test, the microbond test, the microindentation test and the single-fiber fragmentation test [5]. Preliminary tests have shown that the mostly applied single-fiber pull-out is not an appropriate method for the rather thick and brittle PZT fibers. Instead, the single-fiber fragmentation test (SFFT) has been chosen for the experimental investigation of the interfacial adhesion (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Principle of the single-fiber fragmentation test.

In the SFFT, a single fiber is fully embedded in the middle of a dogbone-shaped specimen which in turn consists of the matrix material to be tested. The

specimen is increasingly loaded in tension and the fiber breaks repeatedly into fragments. The so-called fragmentation process proceeds until it reaches the saturation limit. At saturation, the fragments are too short to build up tensile stresses transferred from the matrix to the fiber high enough to provoke further breakage. Fig. 2 illustrates how tensile stresses transferred from the matrix build up in fiber fragments of different lengths [6]. In order to introduce the maximum tensile stress a fiber can bear ($\sigma_{f\max}$), a fragment must have at least the critical length l_c . If a fragment's length is bigger than or equal to l_c and if shear stresses between matrix and fragment are high enough, this fragment can break again. Consequently, the fragments with lengths l_1 and l_2 are too short to build up $\sigma_{f\max}$ and therefore cannot exhibit further breaks [6].

Fig. 2. Build-up of tensile stresses in fiber fragments with different lengths below, equal to and above l_c [6].

The observation of the fragmentation process and the measurement of the fragment lengths are carried out with an optical microscope. The lengths of the fragments can then be used to derive an average value for the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) applying the frequently used constant shear model given by Kelly and Tyson [7]:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_{f\max} \cdot d_f}{2l_c} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), τ represents the IFSS, d_f the fiber diameter and $\sigma_{f\max}$ the fiber tensile strength at critical length. The critical length l_c is defined as 4/3 of the average fragment length.

For the SFFT, a new device has been set up comprising a tensile testing machine (Z2.5, Zwick Roell, Germany), a digital microscope (VHX 100, Keyence, Japan) and stages for x-,y- and z-motion of the objective. The analyzed section of the SFFT

specimens is 40 mm long and has a cross section of $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$. The constant strain rate is 0.08 %/min. The SFFT-specimens are produced with silicone moulds. A photograph of a specimen is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Photograph of a SFFT-specimen with a PZT fiber embedded in epoxy resin.

Tab. 1 shows the selection of epoxy resin matrices. All matrices are room temperature (RT) curable and consist of bisphenol-based resins in combination with aminic hardeners. Different curing conditions are applied to the SFFT-specimens. All specimens are cured at RT. Some specimens are additionally heat treated at elevated temperatures (details concerning the curing conditions are given in section 3).

Tab. 1. Specification of selected epoxy resin matrices including mixing ratios for resin and hardener

matrices				
A	B	C	D	E
resin + hardener (company)				
Araldite® 2020/A + Araldite® 2020/B	L + EPH 500	L + L	L 20 + EPH 161	L 20 + EK 960*
(Huntsman)	(R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe, * Momentive)			
resin : hardener				
100 : 30	100:63	100:40	100:25	100:34

3 Results

Fig. 4 to Fig. 8 display results of the SFFT in terms of fiber breaks-displacement curves for the matrices listed in Tab. 1. In principle, all fiber breaks-displacement curves exhibit S-like

shapes as long as the tested specimens reach saturation of fragmentation. They can be separated into three sections. In the beginning, the strains of the specimens are low and no fiber breaks occur. In the middle section, the total numbers of fiber breaks accumulate causing the curves to rise up with their highest inclinations. In the end section, reaching saturation, the curves show an asymptotic behavior. Accordingly, if specimens do not reach saturation level, their fiber breaks-displacement curves show parts of an S. If the numbers of fiber breaks remain constant three times in a row, saturation of fragmentation is assumed to be achieved. As the determination of a reliable value for the tensile strength at critical length $\sigma_{f_{max}}(l_c)$ of the PZT fibers proves to be difficult, quantitative analyses and comparisons of the SFFT-results are done in terms of critical aspect ratios and numbers of fiber breaks. Fig. 4 shows the fiber breaks-displacement curves of SFFT-specimens with the base material matrix A. Three different curing conditions are tested: exclusive RT curing, additional tempering at 40 °C for 16 h and additional tempering at 60 °C for 3 h (with 5 specimens per curing condition). The curve of the specimen termed “16h 40°C I” shows a non-typical shape. The reason is that, for this specimen, no current values of fiber breaks recorded during the fragmentation process are available but only to total number of fiber breaks. 3 of 5 RT-cured specimens reach saturation level. Their total numbers of fragments are low. This, in turn, means long average fragment lengths which indicate weak adhesion between PZT fibers and matrix. In contrast, the specimens with additional heat treatment do not reach saturation of fragmentation. Nevertheless, their total numbers of fiber breaks are up to 10 times higher compared to the RT-cured specimens. Hence, even without saturation it can already be deduced that the load transfer between fiber and matrix is increased multiple times by additional heat treatment. Furthermore, it can be seen that the specimens tempered at 40 °C range between 50 and 80 fiber breaks whereas the specimens tempered at 60 °C range between 40 and 60 fiber breaks. Taking into account that specimens tempered at 40 °C and specimens tempered at 60 °C exhibit asymptotic behavior which corresponds the final part of the aforementioned S-shape, Fig. 4 suggests the highest interfacial adhesion for the specimens tempered at 40 °C.

Fig. 4. Cumulative number of fiber breaks plotted against displacement of SFFT-specimens with matrix A and different curing conditions (RT, 40 °C, 60 °C)

Results for SFFT-specimens with matrix B can be found in Fig. 5. 5 specimens are exclusively RT-cured and 5 specimens are additionally tempered at 40 °C for 15 h. The initial linear increase of the curve of specimen “15h 40°C III” is simply due to the fact that the current number of fiber breaks for this specimen is only available for displacements > 0.9 mm. For both curing conditions, saturation is reached. The RT-cured specimens are characterized by a rather high degree of scatter of their saturation levels. Their final numbers of fiber breaks range from 13 to 36. The curves of the specimens tempered 40 °C all stagnate in a comparatively narrow window of 40 to 46. Thus, the average fragment lengths are lower after tempering which indicates stronger interfacial adhesion. The named scatter is illustrated more clearly in Fig. 9 in terms of critical aspect ratios l_c/d . It is observable how the critical aspect ratios of the RT-cured specimens decrease with increasing curing time. Lower critical aspect ratios stand for higher interfacial adhesion. Consequently, an increased curing time for the RT-cured specimens with matrix B is accompanied by higher interfacial adhesion. Furthermore, Fig. 9 demonstrates that the RT-cured specimens with longer curing time reach critical aspect ratios almost as low the corresponding values of the heat-treated specimens. Also, it is inferred that the heat treatment removes the scatter apparent for the RT-cured specimens and causes the critical

aspect ratios of the tempered specimens to yield values between 4.0 and 4.6.

Fig. 5. Cumulative number of fiber breaks plotted against displacement of SFFT-specimens with matrix B and different curing conditions (RT, 40 °C)

In Fig. 6, fiber breaks-displacement curves of SFFT-specimens with matrix C are shown. 5 specimens are RT-cured, 7 specimens are tempered at 40 °C for 15 h. The RT-cured specimens mostly achieve saturation of fragmentation (4 of 5) and have between 30 and 60 fiber breaks. The specimens tempered at 40 °C do not reach saturation level. 5 of them fail at displacements between 0.5 mm and 0.8 mm. They fail in the middle section of the S-shaped curve discussed before. Hence, it cannot be said whether their saturation level in terms of fiber breaks would be higher compared to the RT-cured specimens. The specimens “15h 40°C III” and “15h 40°C VII”, however, are somewhat separated from the rest of the specimens. They fail at higher displacements and have fiber breaks between 60 and 80 without achieving saturation. This points towards enhanced load transfer between PZT fiber and matrix C due to additional tempering at 40°C.

Regarding matrix D, 8 SFFT-specimens are cured at RT and 5 specimens are additionally tempered at 100 °C (see Fig. 7). The scatter of the RT-cured specimens is apparent: It ranges from 0 to 77 fiber breaks. This behavior can be attributed to curing time. The first 4 RT-cured specimens I to IV are cured for 2-3 days prior to testing. They range between 0 and 7 fiber breaks. The second 4 specimens V to VIII are RT-cured for 41 days prior to testing, have 22 to 77 fiber breaks and their curves exhibit a much steeper increase of fragments before failure. The specimens with additional heat

treatment show a rather uniform behavior. All curves virtually follow the same path. The steep increases of their curves all set in at about 0.6 mm displacement and all failures occur between 0.6 mm and 0.8 mm displacement. As the heat-treated specimens fail in the steep middle section, no statements can be made concerning the average fragment lengths and the resulting critical aspect ratios.

Fig. 6. Cumulative number of fiber breaks plotted against displacement of SFFT-specimens with matrix C and different curing conditions (RT, 40 °C)

Fig. 7. Cumulative number of fiber breaks plotted against displacement of SFFT-specimens with matrix D and different curing conditions (RT, 100 °C)

Fiber breaks-displacement curves of SFFT-specimens with matrix E and different curing conditions are displayed in Fig. 8. The RT-cured specimens are very brittle and fail quickly. The

specimens tempered at 120 °C fail in the area of 0.7 mm to 0.9 mm. They show similar curves with onsets of the fragmentation process being located quite precisely at about 0.6 mm displacement. Specimens “15h 100°C IV” and “15h 100°C V” have 33 and 36 fiber breaks. The failure of all specimens occurs in the steep middle section or before. Thus, no critical aspect ratios can be derived.

Fig. 8. Cumulative number of fiber breaks plotted against displacement of SFFT-specimens with matrix E and different curing conditions (RT, 120 °C)

Fig. 9. Comparison of critical aspect ratios l_c/d of SFFT-specimens with matrix B and different curing conditions.

In order to quantitatively distinguish the discussed types of SFFT-specimens (five alternative matrices A to E, different curing conditions) in terms of interfacial adhesion, critical aspect ratios can be compared. From the types of SFFT-specimens discussed in Fig. 4 to Fig. 9, the types with matrices A, B and C reach saturation level at RT-curing and therefore allow the calculation of critical aspect

ratios. Moreover, the specimens with matrix B and additional heat treatment reach saturation level. The averaged critical aspect ratios come to 41.2 (matrix A, RT-cured), 8.5 (matrix B, RT-cured), 4.3 (matrix B, additionally tempered at 40 °C), 3.8 (matrix C, RT-cured). Accordingly, the RT-cured SFFT-specimens with matrix C show (on average) the strongest load transfer from fiber to matrix in comparison to the other types that reached saturation. For specimens that do not achieve saturation of fragmentation, however, critical aspect ratios cannot be calculated. Nevertheless, depending on the type of matrix and curing conditions, qualitative statements can be made for some specimen types. Most striking are the specimens with matrix A and additional tempering at i) 40 °C and ii) 60 °C. As Fig. 4 shows, the fragmentation processes of the corresponding specimens have not ended before failure occurs. Anyhow, the specimens have already accumulated high amounts of fiber breaks. Thus, in the case of matrix A, it can be deduced that the averaged critical aspect ratios for the specimens tempered at i) 40 °C and ii) 60 °C are below or equal to 2.5 and 3.4, respectively. It shows that these two types of SFFT-specimens have a more efficient load transfer from the matrix to the fiber than all aforementioned types of specimen at saturation level.

Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 are obtained using polarized light and show photoelastic patterns for SFFT-specimens with matrix A and different curing conditions. Both specimens have reached saturation level. The specimen in Fig. 10 was cured at RT and the specimen in Fig. 11 was additionally tempered at 60 °C. The photoelastic patterns facilitate the localization of the fiber breaks. In Fig. 11, more fiber breaks can be found in contrast to Fig. 10. Accordingly, this implicates shorter fiber fragments for the heat-treated specimen and is therefore a sign of stronger interfacial adhesion. The stress concentrations in the vicinity of the matrix cracks in Fig. 11 indicate efficient load transfer from the matrix to the fiber. Hence, this suggests a clear increase in interfacial adhesion strength achieved by additional tempering.

Fig. 10. Photoelastic patterns of a RT-cured SFFT-specimen with matrix A at saturation.

Fig. 11. Photoelastic patterns of a SFFT-specimen at saturation with matrix A and tempered at 60 °C.

Results of tensile tests for the epoxy resin matrices A, B and C are displayed in Tab. 2 in terms of strains at break. A rule of thumb exists for the SFFT [5] according to which the strain at break of the matrix should be at least three times the value of the embedded fiber in order to reach saturation level in the SFFT. Consequently, if saturation is reached in the SFFT for a matrix with a specific strain at break, another matrix (or the same matrix after additional heat treatment) with a higher strain at break should be expected to also cause saturation. This applies to the results for matrix B in Tab. 2. However, it conflicts with the results for matrices A and C. The strains at break for matrices A and C at RT are 4.11 % and 3.51 %, respectively. The corresponding values after additional tempering at 40 °C are both higher: 7.34 % and 5.02 %. Nonetheless, saturation

level is reached for both matrices if cured at RT but not if additionally tempered at 40 °C.

Tab. 2. Strains at break for matrices A, B and C and different curing conditions obtained from tensile tests in accordance with DIN EN ISO 527 (including standard deviations).

strain at break [%]		
matrix A	matrix B	matrix C
<i>cured at RT</i>		
4.11±0.38 *	16.27±9.57 *	3.51±0.65 *
<i>cured at RT + additionally tempered at 40 °C</i>		
7.34±3.34	17.90±3.11 *	5.02±1.84
* at least 60% of the corresponding SFFT-specimens achieved saturation		

A typical topographic image of the surface of a PZT fiber is depicted in Fig. 12. It is obtained by atomic force microscopy (AFM) and illustrates the coarse grain structure of the material. This characteristic structure is due to the PZT crystals and can also be recognized in the fiber cross section of the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images in Fig. 13 to Fig. 15. The SEM images are obtained from fractographic cross sections of SFFT-specimens with matrix A after tempering at 40 °C. Fig. 13 shows the entire fiber cross section. The mentioned crystals are well visible in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15. Concerning Fig. 14, it can also be seen that, in some locations, fiber and matrix are not in contact (see dashed circle). In Fig. 15, there is no contact along the entire depicted section of the interface. The locations/areas without contact can be related to air trapped within the pores. As the SFFT-specimens are not manufactured and cured under vacuum, air can remain in the porosities of the PZT fibers. Another explanation can be the preparation. Although the fractography aims to avoid distorting effects of preparation techniques such as polishing, it might cause the PZT fibers to partially detach from the matrix.

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Fig. 12. Topographic AFM image of the surface of a PZT fiber with an edge length of 30 μm and an average roughness of 283 nm.

Fig. 13. SEM image of a fractographic cross section of a SFFT-specimen with matrix A after tempering at 40 °C.

Fig. 14. SEM image showing the fiber-matrix interface of a fractographic cross section of a SFFT-specimen with matrix A after tempering at 40 °C.

Fig. 15. SEM image showing the fiber-matrix interface of a fractographic cross section of a SFFT-specimen with matrix A after tempering at 40 °C.

Regarding the application of surface modifications to the PZT fibers mentioned in section 1, preliminary tests have been conducted. SFFT-specimens containing unsized PZT fibers and PZT fibers sized with GLYMO, (3-Glycidioxypropyl)triethoxysilane, were tested. Tab. 3 shows a comparison of the obtained critical aspect ratios. The critical aspect ratio is lower for the sized fiber/matrix specimen. This indicates an enhanced load transfer ability from matrix to PZT fiber.

Tab. 3. Comparison of critical aspect ratios of SFFT-specimens with unsized and sized PZT fibers.

fiber modification	l_c [μm]	d [μm]	critical aspect ratio l_c/d [-]
PZT fiber, unsized	792	276	2.9
PZT fiber sized with GLYMO	493.6	305.7	1.6

4 Conclusion

Single-fiber fragmentation tests sensitively display stress transfer from epoxy matrices to PZT fibers. Significant conclusions can not only be drawn from specimens with saturation of fragmentation but also from certain specimens that fail before. The critical aspect ratios depend on the kind of epoxy resin and the temperature of curing or heat treatment. Besides the variation of storage modulus and glass transition temperature (results not shown here), thermally induced stresses are considered to vary adhesion strength. A more comprehensive and thorough investigation is underway. Furthermore, surface modification of PZT fibers is a challenging task in order to modify the interphase built-up for a gradual change of the Young's modulus between two phases.

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